

JSIR2S Code System For Delayed Radiation Field Calculations

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ABSTRACT

The JSIR2S is a decay radiation field calculation Python based code coupling a modified version of a Monte Carlo particle transport code MCNP v6.1, isotopic inventory activation and transmutation code FISPACT-II and a code for beta decay electron and positron emission spectra calculations BetaShape. The code works by superimposing a rectangular mesh over problem geometry and implements a so-called cell-under-voxel approach, where inventory calculations are treated separately for each cell of the superimposed mesh voxel. Secondary radiation fields of all the delayed particles included in the FISPACT-II calculations can be calculated. Secondary particle emission spectra are characterized by continuous spectra for electrons and positrons from β decay, and exact line spectra for other particles and reactions. An application of the JSIR2S code to the ITER computational shutdown dose rate benchmark is presented and calculated shutdown dose rates compared with other R2S and D1S based systems. The shutdown dose rates are in good agreement.

1 INTRODUCTION

The calculation of the radiation field during and after reactor operation of fission and fusion devices is a major factor in the reactor design due to safety concerns associated with radiation field heating inside fission reactor cores and to radiation exposed fusion device components, exposure of sensitive equipment and its degradation, exposure of maintenance workers during reactor outages and radioactivity after decommissioning. To address the above mentioned challenges, precise delayed radiation calculation tools are required in order to provide adequate radiation shielding [1], for maintenance planning [2], safe irradiation of various samples and experimental equipment [3] and final decommissioning [4]. Lately several computer codes for calculation of gamma shutdown dose rate based on Direct-1-Step (D1S) [5] and Rigorous-2-Step (R2S) [6] methodologies have been introduced. While

these codes display good agreement with fusion shutdown dose-rate measurements, their application on fission devices still remains to be performed. Also, their availability outside their developing institutions is limited.

The JSI Reactor Physics department has also been heavily involved in fusion neutronics and radiation research and the JSI TRIGA reactor utilization has in recent years shifted from neutron irradiation to irradiation in mixed neutron-gamma field. A R2S methodology based Python code, coupling Monte Carlo transport code MCNP v6.1 [7], FISPACT-II isotopic activation and transmutation code [8] and beta decay emission spectra calculation code BetaShape [9] has been under development for the last year in order to be able to independently calculate shutdown dose rates in fusion facilities and to be able to fully characterize the JSI TRIGA reactor irradiation facilities, including the radiation due to radioactive decay of fission and activation products.

As part of the code validation process we present the shutdown dose rate calculation results of a computational model of a neutron irradiation and shutdown dose rate measurement experiment on an ITER-like port plug obtained by the JSIR2S code system, and compare the results with ones calculated by other D1S and R2S codes.

2 JSIR2S CODE SYSTEM

The JSIR2S code system is a code for calculating numerous types of decay radiation field in the MCNP model geometry. Its potential utilizations range from calculating the shutdown dose rate, assuring the safe environment for maintenance workers during reactor outages and for waste qualification after reactor decommissioning, calculations of self powered neutron detector (SPND) response functions to determination of Cherenkov radiation and for qualification of the radiation field inside reactor irradiation facilities in general. In contrast to similar D1S and R2S codes which usually only have the delayed gamma simulation capability, the JSIR2S code system enables the simulation of all decay radiation fields and their secondary products (for instance electrons due to gamma interaction).

The JSIR2S code system is written in Python and couples together a modified version of the MCNP v6.1 Monte Carlo particle transport code which handles the transport of primary radiation (e.g. neutrons), as well as secondary radiation field due to activation and transmutation, which is being calculated by the FISPACT-II code, with β^+ positron and β^- electron emission spectra calculated by the BetaShape code.

The code system calculates the changes in isotopic inventory and associated radiation field on the MCNP model geometry by superimposing a rectangular mesh and implementing a so called cell-under-voxel approach, where isotopic vector changes due to primary radiation activation and/or transmutation are separately calculated in each geometry cell inside the mesh voxel, used also by the R2SUNED code system [10], which is in effect a combination of a cell based and mesh based volume averaged neutron flux tally (Figure 1).

Due to irregular volume shapes arising from combined cell and mesh division, stochastic calculations of cells under each mesh voxel volumes to user defined precision has been implemented. Isotopic composition densities are extracted from the MCNP model and in conjunction with volumes used to calculate the initial isotopic inventory. The irradiation procedure such as primary particle radiation (e.g. neutron or proton activation) source strength and irradiation duration are supplied by the user in terms of source multiplication factors for both fixed and eigenvalue source terms and in terms of irradiation and cooling times. The changes in model geometry not associated with isotopic inventory, such as changes in water density (if water is not considered for activation), can also be taken into account by assigning different MCNP model geometries at different irradiation times.

Figure 1: 2D representation of different volume based tally boundaries for a cylinder with superimposed mesh. Tally volume bounds are marked with red line.

Secondary particle emission spectra and intensity libraries are prepared by extracting the emission line spectra from FISPACT-II code and by evaluating the entire ENSDF database with the BetaShape code for β^+ and β^- continuous emission spectra. Secondary particle emission spectra are then calculated according to changes in the isotopic inventory and used to generate secondary particle source description files for each secondary particle type and for each user specified time step. The files are then used with a modified version of the MCNP 6.1 with a custom source routine, enabling the generation of particles according to secondary source description file specifications. Current implementation supports the sampling of secondary particle location and energy by its intensity. In some cases it may be desired to perform uniform sampling, and adjust particle weight by its sampling probability.

The code system has been written to minimize the required computational time by making use of multi-core parallelism of modern computer processors in the computation intensive parts of the code. For example a single calculation of delayed radiation spectrum on a single core takes roughly 10 s, which inflates dramatically over large models, where more than 1×10^5 mesh voxels are used. A simplified work-flow scheme of the JSIR2S code system is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: JSI R2S work-flow representation. Red squares around inventory calculations of the code denote parallel executions of single core inventory and secondary radiation source specification. Multiple purple squares around decay particle transport section denote multiple MCNP runs for different time steps and decay radiation types. Yellow squares denote user specified data, green squares denote a single MCNP calculation, and the blue square denotes decay data library preparation.

3 ITER PORT PLUG SHUTDOWN DOSE RATE BENCHMARK

The JSIR2S code system is currently undergoing the validation process, before being offered to a wider scientific community. As part of the validation process it has been applied to the ITER shutdown dose rate benchmarking exercise [11]. The model consist of a cylindrical assembly, closely resembling the ITER equatorial port element. A schematic of problem geometry is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: ITER port plug model cross section, comprised of an iron cylinder and a disc (in blue) and homogeneous mixture of water and iron (in red). Isotropic source term emitting 14 MeV neutrons is simulated in the green disc (void), while shutdown dose rate is tallied in violet plate cells (void). All the measurements are in cm.

The assembly is irradiated by 14 MeV neutrons from an isotropic neutron source, following the SA2 ITER reference irradiation scenario for nuclear analysis, described in Table 1. The benchmarking quantity is the dose rate in the above described tally cells, 1×10^6 s after the end of irradiation.

For the calculations a mesh with voxel size of $4 \text{ cm} \times 4 \text{ cm} \times 4.015 \text{ cm}$ was superimposed over the problem geometry, and cells depicted with red and blue color in Figure 3 were used for the activation calculations. The source term was biased from isotropic towards the port plug and

normalized accordingly in order to decrease the required computational time. Mesh based variance reduction weight windows using the ADVANTG code [12] was utilized to obtain neutron flux results with sufficiently low variance 3.1. Neutron flux was tallied in the VITAMIN-J 175 [13] energy group structure. FENDL 2.1 nuclear data libraries [14] were used for particle transport calculations and EAF2010 activation library [15] was used for activation and secondary particle spectra determination. Isotopic concentration down to $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ were considered, which underestimates the total activity by a factor of relative factor of 1×10^{-6} . ICRP-74 flux to dose conversion factors were used for dose rate tally calculations [16]. 1×10^9 source particles with weight window variance reduction technique were used in the neutron transport problem and 4×10^9 secondary photons were simulated without any biasing for the dose rate calculations.

Table 1: Table of neutron source strengths, irradiation times and repetitions of the SA2-ITER irradiation scenario, divided into three separate, consecutive stages.

Source strength [n/s]	Duration	Repetitions
1.0714×10^{17}	2 years	1
8.25×10^{17}	10 years	1
0	0.667 years	1
1.6607×10^{18}	1.33 years	1
0	3920 s	17
2.0×10^{19}	400 s	17
0	3920 s	4
2.8×10^{19}	400 s	4

3.1 ADVANTG

The **A**utomate**D** **V**aria**N**ce reduc**T**ion **G**enerator (ADVANTG) [12] code was used to determine variance reduction parameters for this thick shielding problem. A fine non-uniform spatial mesh was determined based on several iterations with approximately $280 \times 280 \times 60$ spatial voxels alongside a detailed quadrature set. The 27 neutron energy group shielding library included with the ADVANTG distribution based on the ENDF/B-VII.0 [17] evaluation nuclear data library was found to be sufficient for this problem. The Forward-Weighted Consistent Adjoint Driven Importance Sampling (FW-CADIS) method was used with the option to produce uniform uncertainties throughout the mesh based tally. To ensure low uncertainties in all energy groups of the VITAMIN-J 175 group structure, the FW-CADIS response weighting option was turned off. ADVANTG generated variance reduction parameters produced uncertainties throughout the problem and for each energy group equal or below 1% when 1×10^9 source particles were simulated with MCNP.

3.2 RESULTS

In this section we present total neutron flux and weight windows as calculated by the ADVANTG code throughout the model geometry, and the final dose rates in the tally cells of the computational benchmark. The weight windows for 6.37 MeV to 20 MeV generated by the ADVANTG code are presented in Figure 4. Neutron fluence per source neutron simulated is presented in Figure 5. Since source biasing towards the ITER port plug model was used, total neutron fluxes for each irradiation step are obtained by multiplying one half of the source strength with the per source neutron values.

Figure 4: Weight windows for neutrons between 6.37 MeV to 20 MeV as calculated by the ADVANTG code.

Figure 5: Neutron fluence per source simulated inside the model geometry.

Both uniform sampling with weight adjustment and probability based sampling. Due to the least activated part of the port plug model at the tally cell side, undersampling of the problem using the probability based sampling is expected. 4×10^9 secondary particles were simulated for the probability sampling case and 1×10^8 particles for the case with uniform sampling with weight adjustment. The JSIR2S code system shutdown dose rate results are presented in Figure 6 and compared with numerous other codes [11], generally showing good agreement in both cases. As expected, the dose rate results using the probability based sampling undersample the secondary particle source, hence the large uncertainties and a slight dose-rate underestimation. Results using the uniform sampling with weight adjustment are in perfect agreement with other codes.

Figure 6: Shutdown dose rate, as calculated by different D1S and R2S methodology codes vs. tally cell outer radius. The JSIR2S code system calculated dose rates are denoted with 'P' for probability based, and with 'U' for uniform based sampling with weight adjustment. The error-bars denote statistical uncertainty due to secondary particle transport only. No error estimations from other codes are given.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The JSIR2S code system for decay radiation field calculations has been applied to the ITER computational shutdown dose rate benchmark, showing good agreement with other shutdown dose rate codes. Further code validation on both fission and fusion experimental data and for other decay particle types will be performed in the near future. Future versions will also include uniform secondary particle sampling capability with the possibility of generating a simplified MCNP fixed source description file to use with the ADVANTG code for secondary particle transport variance reduction. The code is also being expanded to automate depletion and burn-up calculations on fission problems and to calculate decay heat generation.

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